
JSA (Joseph S. Angga) Fraction Beads: Bridging Conceptual Learning Gaps

Joseph S. Angga¹

¹ *Catalunan Grande Elementary School, Department of Education, Division of Davao City*

Reception date of the manuscript: 18/05/2024

Acceptance date of the manuscript: 18/05/2024

Publication date: 20/05/2024

Summary— The "JSA Fraction Beads" innovation, developed by Joseph S. Angga, addresses significant challenges in mathematics education by offering a hands-on, interactive tool designed to enhance students' conceptual understanding of fractions and related mathematical concepts. This educational tool comprises 12 stainless steel bars with 18 spherical wooden beads on each bar, providing a tangible representation of abstract mathematical ideas. The innovation aims to overcome the shortcomings of traditional rote memorization methods, which often fail to engage students and build a solid conceptual foundation. The primary objective of JSA Fraction Beads is to improve student engagement, comprehension, and problem-solving skills in mathematics. By allowing students to physically manipulate fractions, this tool helps bridge the gap between abstract concepts and concrete understanding, fostering deeper comprehension and retention. The innovation is designed to be inclusive, accommodating diverse learning styles and abilities, and can be seamlessly integrated into existing curricula. The implementation of JSA Fraction Beads involves several stages, including planning, resource gathering, training for educators, and continuous assessment and refinement. Teachers are equipped with comprehensive manuals and training sessions to effectively incorporate the beads into their lessons. The innovation not only aims to improve students' mathematical proficiency but also to reignite their interest in the subject, ultimately leading to better academic performance and a more inclusive, effective learning environment.

Keywords— Fraction, Student Engagement, Mathematics, Numeracy Innovation

I. OVERVIEW

I have encountered numerous students grappling with the challenge of solving both routine and non-routine word problems. This difficulty often stems from a fundamental struggle to grasp underlying mathematical concepts. Many students lack a solid understanding of key mathematical principles, making it challenging for them to apply their knowledge effectively in problem-solving scenarios. These kinds of problems can significantly impede learners' overall mathematical proficiency (Kaur 2009). Traditional teaching methods often struggle to effectively engage students, resulting in disinterest and detachment from the learning process (Stipek Byler, 2004). Traditional approaches often prioritize rote memorization of formulas and techniques without ensuring a solid conceptual foundation. This problem reflects the performance of our learners in mathematics.

In the PISA 2018 International Report, Filipino students' average score in mathematical literacy was 353 points, significantly lower than the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) average of 489 points, indicating a below Level 1 proficiency (OECD, 2019). The

Philippines also scored 297 in math in the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (Mullis et al., 2019).

Addressing these challenges in mathematics education can have several positive impacts on the educational system, its stakeholders, and the community at large: By implementing innovative teaching strategies like the JSA Fraction Beads and prioritizing conceptual understanding over rote memorization, students are more likely to develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. This can lead to improved academic performance and overall learning outcomes. Engaging teaching methods that prioritize conceptual understanding can help reignite students' interest and motivation in mathematics. Students are more likely to actively participate in lessons and develop a positive attitude towards learning. Innovative teaching strategies can help reduce achievement gaps among students from different socioeconomic backgrounds. A stronger mathematics education system benefits the broader community by producing well-educated individuals who are better equipped to contribute positively to society.

Additionally, addressing educational disparities can promote social equity and economic development within the community. Addressing these challenges positively impacts the educational system by fostering a more inclusive, engag-

ing, and effective learning environment that benefits students, educators, and the community.

The innovation directly tackles the identified problems in mathematics education through various key features and aspects. Firstly, it offers a tangible representation of abstract concepts, such as fractions, which are often challenging for students to grasp. By providing physical manipulatives that students can interact with, the innovation bridges the gap between abstract mathematical ideas and concrete understanding, making concepts more accessible and comprehensible.

Moreover, since the strategy prioritizes conceptual understanding over rote memorization, it diverges from traditional teaching methods that often lead to surface-level learning and encourages students to actively engage in meaningful exploration and discovery, promoting deeper comprehension and critical thinking skills.

Additionally, the JSA Fraction Beads can be adapted to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities, promoting inclusivity and personalized learning experiences. By integrating into existing curricula and instructional practices, the innovation ensures continuity and coherence in mathematics education, supporting long-term learning and mastery of essential concepts.

This innovation offers a holistic approach to addressing challenges in mathematics education, promoting active engagement, conceptual understanding, and personalized instruction for all students. This innovation is intricately aligned with the mission, vision, and objectives of the Department of Education, serving as a catalyst for student-centered mathematics education and ensuring equitable access to high-quality learning experiences. Rooted in the department's mission to deliver quality education for all, this strategy facilitates active engagement with mathematical concepts, fostering deep comprehension and proficiency among students.

Moreover, it resonates with the department's vision of preparing learners for success in an ever-evolving world by nurturing critical thinking, problem-solving, and mathematical reasoning skills. In terms of objectives, the JSA Fraction Beads innovation directly contributes to enhancing teaching and learning quality, improving student outcomes, and promoting inclusivity and equity in education. By empowering educators with a versatile tool that enhances teaching practices and addresses diverse learning needs, this innovation embodies the department's commitment to innovation, excellence, and equity in education.

The JSA Fraction Beads innovation embodies the core principles and values reflected in the SDO's mantra by prioritizing student-centered learning, inclusivity, and innovation in mathematics education. The innovation aligns with the SDO's commitment to fostering a culture of excellence and equity in education, ensuring that all learners have the opportunity to succeed.

By providing a hands-on, interactive approach to learning mathematics, the JSA Fraction Beads strategy promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among students, empowering them to become confident and proficient mathematicians. Additionally, the innovation promotes inclusivity by accommodating diverse learning styles and needs, allowing students of varying abilities to access and participate in mathematical learning experiences

effectively.

Furthermore, the innovation serves to advance the SDO's goals of improving teaching quality, enhancing student outcomes, and fostering innovation in education. As educators integrate the strategy into their teaching practices, they are equipped with a versatile tool that enhances the effectiveness of mathematics instruction, leading to improved student learning outcomes.

Moreover, by encouraging creativity and innovation in teaching and learning, the JSA Fraction Beads strategy supports the SDO's efforts to promote continuous improvement and innovation in education. The innovation not only reflects the core principles and values of the SDO but also contributes significantly to advancing its goals of excellence, equity, and innovation in education.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

As a teaching device the JSA Fraction Beads is characterized by its practical and durable design. Comprising of 12 stainless steel bars, with 18 spherical wooden beads in every bar, this tactile tool is meticulously crafted to ensure smooth manipulation by students' fingers. This design fosters hands-on exploration and interaction with mathematical concepts, promoting deeper understanding. The stainless-steel frame offers durability and stability, guaranteeing longevity and resilience to frequent use in classroom settings. Beyond its foundational purpose in teaching fractions, the JSA Fraction Beads extends its utility to embrace more advanced mathematical concepts, such as problem-solving techniques. This versatility significantly alleviates the workload of teachers, as the material caters to nearly every topic within the mathematics curriculum. Unlike traditional manipulative materials, the JSA Fraction Beads is exceptionally easy to prepare, saving valuable instructional time and effort.

Furthermore, the interactive nature of the JSA Fraction Beads fosters student engagement during break times. Students eagerly manipulate the beads, creating opportunities for peer tutoring and cooperative learning experiences. This engagement not only reinforces mathematical concepts but also promotes collaboration and social interaction among students, enhancing overall classroom dynamics. As a strategy, the JSA Fraction Beads innovation represents a comprehensive and versatile approach to teaching mathematics, designed to enhance conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills among students. The tactile materials serve as tangible representations of abstract mathematical concepts, enabling students to explore and manipulate fractions in a hands-on manner.

Furthermore, the JSA Fraction Beads innovation promotes active learning and student engagement through collaborative activities, problem-solving tasks, and real-world applications. By fostering a dynamic and interactive learning environment, the innovation encourages students to take ownership of their learning and develop critical thinking skills essential for mathematical proficiency. The innovation represents a powerful tool for transforming mathematics education, offering educators a versatile and effective means of enhancing student learning experiences and outcomes. With its emphasis on hands-on exploration, visual representation, and collaborative learning, the innovation empowers students

to develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts.

The innovation operates by providing a tangible and interactive tool that effectively addresses the identified challenges in mathematics education. Through hands-on manipulation of the beads, students are able to bridge the gap between abstract mathematical concepts and real-world applications, thereby enhancing their understanding and proficiency in fractions and other related topics. The tactile nature of the beads facilitates kinesthetic learning, allowing students to physically engage with mathematical concepts and visualize fractions in a concrete manner. Furthermore, the versatility of the JSA Fraction Beads enables teachers to tailor their instruction to meet the diverse needs of students. Additionally, the JSA Fraction Beads streamline the teaching process by providing a ready-made resource that is easy to prepare and use in the classroom. Teachers can quickly set up activities and demonstrations using the beads, saving valuable instructional time and effort.

Moreover, the durability of the beads ensures that they can be used repeatedly without the need for frequent replacement, making them a cost-effective and sustainable solution for mathematics education. By promoting hands-on learning, accommodating diverse learning needs, and streamlining the teaching process, this innovation helps to enhance student learning outcomes. The JSA Fraction Beads strategy offers several distinct advantages and unique capabilities compared to existing solutions or approaches in mathematics education. Firstly, they provide a tangible representation of mathematical concepts, allowing students to physically manipulate fractions, percent, and other entities for enhanced understanding and retention. Its versatility is another key feature, enabling educators to easily integrate them into various lessons across the mathematics curriculum. Through hands-on learning, students actively engage with the beads, leading to deeper comprehension and heightened motivation.

Additionally, educators can customize the use of the beads to accommodate diverse learning preferences and abilities. With user-friendly design and comprehensive instructional materials, the JSA Fraction Beads is easy to implement in the classroom, ensuring quick integration into teaching practice. In summary, the JSA Fraction Beads strategy offers a unique blend of tangible representation, versatility, hands-on learning, customization, ease of use, and sustainability, making them an innovative and effective tool for enhancing mathematical understanding and engagement among students.

This innovation also integrates various technologies, methodologies, and principles to optimize its effectiveness in mathematics education. The innovation harnesses the power of tactile manipulatives, such as fraction beads, to provide students with hands-on learning experiences. These physical materials serve as a foundational component, enabling students to interact directly with mathematical concepts and deepen their understanding. Complementing this tactile approach, the innovation leverages digital technologies to enhance learning experiences further. Educators may incorporate interactive whiteboards, educational apps, or online simulations to supplement hands-on activities with virtual manipulatives or multimedia resources. By integrating these technologies, the innovation caters to diverse learning styles and preferences, ensuring accessibility and engagement for all students. The innovation aligns with pedagogical

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

best practices, emphasizing conceptual understanding, active learning, and differentiated instruction.

Educators are encouraged to facilitate inquiry-based activities, scaffold learning experiences, and plan instruction to meet the unique needs of each learner. By integrating these methodologies and principles, the innovation promotes deep learning, critical thinking, and mathematical proficiency among students. This innovation represents a holistic approach to mathematics education, blending tactile manipulatives, digital technologies, and pedagogical strategies to achieve its intended outcomes effectively.

To use the beads effectively, educators typically provide students with a set of JSA Fraction Beads and guide them through interactive activities and exercises. For example, students can use the beads to represent fractions by placing a certain number of beads on each bar to represent the numerator and denominator of the fraction. They can then manipulate the beads to perform addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division of fractions, enabling them to visualize and understand the underlying concepts. Examples:

a. Fraction Concept

In the actual material, there are 12 bars with 18 beads in every bar. But here only 3 bars are used with 5 beads in each bar. The first bar or the upper most bar of the material is intended to represent the whole which is divided into many parts. Figure 1 shows the whole is divided into 2 equal parts. The second bar is intended to be empty to separate the whole number from the parts below and the next bar is the numerator. The fraction in the third bar is $1/2$ because one is one-half of 2

The improper fraction in the third bar is $2/2$ or 1 whole. This is improper fraction because the numerator and denominator are equal. When the numerator and denominator are equal the number is 1. It means that the whole is divided into certain parts and all of the parts are there nothing more nothing less as shown in Figure 2.

The improper fraction in the third bar is $4/2$ or simply 2 as in Figure 3.

in figure 4, the first bar contains a whole that is divided

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

into 3 equal parts. The third bar shows one part out of three parts so that is $1/3$. The fourth bar contains 2 out of 3 parts, that is $2/3$. The fifth bar contains three-thirds which is equal to one whole. As seen in the first bar which represents one whole. The sixth bar is $4/3$ or $1\frac{1}{3}$. Three of the 4 parts will make a whole then 1 part is $1/3$, so in total the mixed number is $1\frac{1}{3}$. The 7th bar is $5/3$. This improper fraction can be changed into $1\frac{2}{3}$ as 3 of the 5 parts will make a whole and the 2 parts will make $2/3$. The 8th bar has six thirds, three of it will make a whole so since there are two groups of three thirds, it means there are 2 in all.

b. Equivalent Fraction

The first bar in figure 5 shows one whole that is divided into 4 equal parts. There are 2 beads in the second bar that means the fraction is $2/4$, indicating the parts of the whole that is divided into 4 equal parts. In the fourth bar, there are also 2 beads but is labeled $1/2$, indicating that the whole is divided into 2 equal parts and 1 part is being considered. Here every group contains 2 beads. This means that $2/4$ and $1/2$ are equivalent fractions.

Figure 6 shows 1 whole divided into $2/4$ equal parts. It

Fig. 5: Enter Caption

Fig. 6: Enter Caption

Fig. 7: Enter Caption

has 6 rows of 4 beads each row, and 4 columns with 6 beads per column making every bead $1/24$. The fraction $18/24$ for example, can be visualized as equal to $9/12$. The parts boxed with blue color is $18/24$ but if they are to be grouped into groups of 2, there will be 9 groups within the box and 12 groups of 2 for the entire 24 beads. So $18/24$ is equal to $9/12$.

In figure 7, the parts of the whole boxed with color blue is $18/24$. If the beads are grouped into groups of 3, there will be 6 groups inside the blue box and 8 groups for the entire 24 beads. So $18/24 = 6/8$. In figure 8 the parts of the whole boxed with color blue is $18/24$. If the beads are grouped into groups of 6, there will be 3 groups inside the blue box and 4 groups for the entire 24 beads. So $18/24 = 3/4$.

so $18/24$, $9/12$, and $3/4$ are equivalent fractions where $3/4$ is the lowest term fraction. Since 6 is the biggest number of beads in every group then 6 is the greatest common factor of 18 and 24.

c. Adding Similar Fraction

1. What is the sum of $3/4$, $2/4$ and $5/4$?

The beads in figure 9 shows 1 whole divided into 4 equal

Fig. 8: Enter Caption

Fig. 9: Enter Caption

Fig. 10: Enter Caption

parts as indicated in the right side of the first bar. The third bar show $3/4$, the fourth bar shows $2/4$, and $5/4$ in the fifth bar. 4 green colored beads make a whole as well as the 4 blue colored beads and the yellow-colored beads make $2/4$ or $1/2$ therefore the sum of $3/4$, $2/4$, and $5/4$ is $10/4$ or $2 \frac{2}{4}$ or $2 \frac{1}{2}$

d. D. Adding Dissimilar Fraction

1. Find the sum of $2/3$ and $1/2$.

In adding dissimilar fraction, a whole that can represent the given fractions, in this case $2/3$ and $1/2$ is to be figured out first. 3 as the number of times the whole is divided can be used so that 2 beads can represent $2/3$ but the problem is $1/2$ can not be represented by just using 3 beads as shown in figure 10.

To address this, another set of 3 beads will be added making the whole having 6 beads (figure 11).

Thus, the sum of $2/3$ and $1/2$ is $7/6$ or $1 \frac{1}{6}$. The 6 green colored beads make a whole and 1 bead is $1/6$.

e. Subtracting Dissimilar Fraction

In Figure 12, the 4 beads represent $2/3$ and the 3 yellow beads represent $1/2$. If 3 beads are to be taken away from four beads. There will be 1 bead left which represents $1/6$.

f. Multiplying Whole Number by Mixed Number

In figure 13, The right side of the first bar shows 1 whole that is divided into 2 equal parts. The third bar shows $2 \frac{1}{2}$, as every 2 beads make a whole. The fourth and the fifth bars also show $2 \frac{1}{2}$. In other words, the three bars show 3 groups of $2 \frac{1}{2}$, which is equal to $15/2$ or $7 \frac{1}{2}$.

In Figure 14, the number of beads to represent one group is 3 as found in the first bar. The 3rd to 6th bars represents the multiplier which is $3 \frac{1}{3}$ groups with 10 beads arranged orderly.

In figure 15, the first bar of the multiplicand which is in this case $3 \frac{1}{4}$ or $1 \frac{3}{4}$. It is distributed equally into 3 beads making the value of every bead $1/3$. Since there are 10 beads in total and every bead has

Fig. 11: Enter Caption

1. $\frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{2} = ?$

Fig. 12: Enter Caption

1. $3 \times 2 \frac{1}{2}$

This means 3 groups of $2 \frac{1}{2}$

Fig. 13: Enter Caption

2. $3 \frac{1}{3} \times 3 \frac{1}{4}$

Fig. 14: Enter Caption

Fig. 15: Enter Caption

1. $1 \frac{3}{4} \div \frac{1}{3} = ?$

Fig. 16: Dividing Fractions

a value of $13/12$, the product will be $10 \times 13/12$ or $130/12$ or $10 \frac{5}{6}$.

g. Dividing Fractions

Since there are 12 beads for 1 whole, $1 \frac{3}{4}$ shall have 21 beads as shown in the figure 16.

Since the whole is divided into 12 parts, $1/3$ of it shall be 4 beads. So to divide $1 \frac{3}{4}$ divided by $1/3$ is to group the $1 \frac{3}{4}$ or the 21 beads into groups of 4 beads each group.

Since the dividend is represented by 21 beads and the divisor is represented by 4 beads so the quotient will be $5 \frac{1}{4}$ as reflected in figure 18.

A comprehensive guide detailing the utilization of the JSA Fraction Beads strategy is readily available within the manual that I made. This manual serves as a comprehensive resource, offering detailed instructions, examples, and strategies for integrating the fraction beads into mathematics instruction effectively. Additionally, the manual provides valuable insights into facilitating interactive and engaging learning experiences, encouraging exploration, problem-solving, and critical thinking among students. By consulting this manual, educators can confidently incorporate the JSA Fraction Beads strategy into their teaching practices, ensuring optimal learning outcomes for their students.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

The JSA Fraction Beads innovation is designed to achieve several key objectives within the educational context. First and foremost, it aims to enhance students' conceptual understanding of mathematical concepts, particularly fractions, by offering a tangible and interactive tool for exploration and manipulation. Through hands-on experiences with the beads, students can visualize abstract mathematical concepts in a

Fig. 17: Dividing Fractions

Fig. 18: Dividing Fractions

Fig. 19: Dividing Fractions

concrete manner, leading to deeper comprehension and retention.

Additionally, the innovation seeks to foster active engagement among students by providing opportunities for exploration, experimentation, and discovery during mathematics lessons. By actively participating in hands-on activities with the beads, students are more likely to remain focused and motivated, leading to improved learning outcomes. Furthermore, the JSA Fraction Beads innovation aims to promote mathematical proficiency and fluency in problem-solving and critical thinking skills. By integrating the beads into instruction, educators can create dynamic learning experiences that cater to diverse learning needs and abilities, supporting differentiated instruction.

Ultimately, the innovation strives to increase student motivation and interest in mathematics, thereby contributing to improved academic achievement and success. Through its multifaceted approach to teaching and learning, the JSA Fraction Beads innovation aims to revolutionize mathematics education and empower students to become confident and proficient mathematicians.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

The key steps or stages involved in the process flow or framework of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation begin with planning and preparation, where teachers collaborate to identify suitable mathematical concepts and grade levels for integration. Once determined, materials are procured and assembled, ensuring each classroom has sufficient resources. Educators then undergo training to familiarize themselves with the beads and learn effective teaching strategies. Integration into instruction follows, with educators designing lesson plans centered around hands-on manipulation of the beads to teach abstract mathematical concepts. Ongoing assessment and reflection are integral, allowing educators to monitor student progress and adjust instruction as necessary. Documentation of experiences and sharing of best practices contribute to the continuous improvement and dissemination of the in-

novation among educators.

These steps are interconnected and complement each other to ensure the smooth functioning of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation. Planning and preparation lay the groundwork by aligning instructional goals with mathematical concepts and grade levels, guiding subsequent actions. The procurement and assembly of materials facilitate hands-on learning experiences, providing educators with the necessary resources to implement the strategy effectively. Training sessions empower educators with the knowledge and skills needed to utilize the beads in their teaching, fostering confidence and competence. Integration into instruction allows teachers to apply their training directly, engaging students in meaningful learning experiences that bridge the gap between abstract concepts and concrete understanding. Ongoing assessment and reflection enable educators to evaluate student progress and instructional effectiveness, informing adjustments to optimize learning outcomes. Finally, documentation and sharing of experiences promote collaboration and continuous improvement, ensuring that the innovation evolves in response to the needs of educators and students alike.

Certainly, within the process flow or framework of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation, a variety of methodologies, tools, and techniques are integrated to streamline its operations and maximize its impact. These encompass differentiated instruction, scaffolding, formative assessment, cooperative learning, inquiry-based learning, and metacognition. Differentiated instruction ensures that teaching approaches cater to diverse learning styles and abilities, while scaffolding gradually increases task complexity to support students as they build upon their knowledge. Through formative assessment, educators continuously monitor student progress and adjust instruction, accordingly, promoting deeper understanding. Cooperative learning fosters collaboration among students, encouraging peer support and enriching the learning experience. Additionally, inquiry-based learning encourages hands-on exploration and critical thinking, while metacognition empowers students to reflect on their learning processes. By incorporating these methodologies, tools, and techniques into its framework, the JSA Fraction Beads innovation optimizes efficiency and effectiveness, fostering enhanced student engagement and achievement in mathematics.

b. Project Management

The management of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation involves various stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, and potentially external partners such as educational suppliers or technology developers. Educators play a central role in implementing the innovation within their classrooms, utilizing the fraction beads as a teaching tool to enhance instruction and facilitate student learning. Administrators provide support by allocating resources, fostering a culture of innovation, and ensuring that the necessary training and professional development opportunities are available for educators. External partners, such as educational suppliers, may be involved in providing the materials needed for the innovation or supporting its implementation through collaborative initiatives or funding opportunities. Overall, effective management of the innovation requires collaboration and coordi-

nation among all stakeholders to ensure its successful implementation and sustained impact on teaching and learning.

The project management of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation involves several strategies and methodologies to ensure its successful execution. First and foremost, a comprehensive project plan is developed to outline the objectives, scope, timelines, and resource requirements of the innovation. This plan serves as a roadmap for all stakeholders involved in the project. Effective communication and collaboration with stakeholders, including educators, administrators, and external partners, are essential aspects of stakeholder engagement. Regular meetings, updates, and feedback sessions help to keep stakeholders informed and engaged throughout the project. Adequate resources, including funding, materials, and personnel, are allocated to support the implementation of the innovation. This may involve securing budgetary allocations, sourcing materials, and assigning roles and responsibilities to project team members. Potential risks and challenges associated with the innovation are identified and mitigated through proactive risk management strategies. Contingency plans are developed to address unforeseen obstacles and ensure project continuity. Educators and other stakeholders involved in the implementation of the innovation are provided with training and professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge. This ensures that they are equipped to effectively utilize the fraction beads and integrate them into their instructional practices. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are put in place to assess the progress and impact of the innovation. Key performance indicators are identified to measure success against predefined objectives, and regular evaluations are conducted to identify areas for improvement and refinement. By employing these project management strategies and methodologies, the successful execution of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation is ensured, ultimately leading to improved teaching and learning outcomes in mathematics.

The successful management and implementation of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation involve a diverse group of key stakeholders and team members, each contributing unique expertise and perspectives to the project. Educators play a central role in the implementation process, responsible for integrating the fraction beads into their instructional practices and facilitating meaningful learning experiences for students. Curriculum developers collaborate closely with educators to align the innovation with curriculum standards and learning objectives, ensuring its seamless integration into existing mathematics curricula. Administrators provide strategic direction and support, overseeing the overall implementation process and allocating resources as needed. They also play a crucial role in securing buy-in from school leadership and fostering a supportive environment for innovation adoption. Additionally, external partners, such as educational consultants, researchers, and community organizations, may contribute valuable insights and resources to enhance the effectiveness of the innovation. Each stakeholder and team member brings unique perspectives and expertise to the table, collectively contributing to the successful management and implementation of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation.

c. Timeline

The estimated timeline for the pre-implementation stage of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation is 4 to 5 weeks to ensure thorough planning and resource gathering. The planning phase involves defining project goals, identifying key stakeholders, and establishing a project timeline and budget. This phase may take approximately one week, depending on the availability of resources. Simultaneously, efforts to gather necessary resources, such as materials for constructing the fraction beads, may begin during the planning phase. This may involve sourcing materials, procuring equipment, and securing funding or grants to support the project. Resource gathering activities may continue throughout the pre-implementation stage and beyond, as needed.

The implementation stage of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation is a critical phase that involves the actual deployment and utilization of the manipulative materials in classroom settings. This stage typically spans several months and includes various milestones, key tasks, and checkpoints to monitor progress effectively. Initially, teachers undergo training and orientation sessions lasting approximately one month, during which they receive instruction on how to effectively incorporate the JSA Fraction Beads into their mathematics lessons. Following this, a two-month period is dedicated to integrating the beads into classroom instruction, with ongoing support and monitoring provided to teachers. Over the subsequent three months, professional development workshops and collaborative planning sessions are conducted to further enhance teachers' skills and refine the implementation process. Additionally, formative assessments are administered to gauge student progress, with data analyzed and feedback gathered to inform adjustments and improvements. Finally, a month-long period is dedicated to reviewing outcomes, reflecting on experiences, and identifying lessons learned for future iterations. Through regular checkpoints and progress reviews, the implementation process ensures that the innovation is effectively managed and monitored to achieve its intended goals and outcomes. Following the implementation phase, the post-implementation stage of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation is characterized by ongoing evaluation, refinement, and potential expansion to maximize its impact and sustainability. This phase involves continuous monitoring and assessment of the innovation's effectiveness in achieving its intended outcomes. Data collected from formative and summative assessments, as well as feedback from teachers and students, are analyzed to identify strengths, areas for improvement, and emerging needs. Based on these insights, refinements and modifications are made to the implementation approach, instructional strategies, and support mechanisms to enhance efficacy and address challenges effectively. Moreover, professional development opportunities and capacity-building initiatives are provided to educators to ensure their ongoing mastery of the innovation and its integration into classroom practice. As part of a cyclical process, feedback loops are established to facilitate regular communication and collaboration among stakeholders, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation. Additionally, the potential for expansion and scalability of the innovation is explored, considering factors such as resource availability, stakeholder readiness,

and alignment with broader educational goals and priorities. Through systematic evaluation, refinement, and potential expansion, the post-implementation phase ensures that the JSA Fraction Beads innovation remains dynamic, responsive, and impactful in meeting the evolving needs of learners and educators.

d. Resource Utilization

The primary resources utilized during the creation and operation of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation encompass a variety of components. Material resources include stainless steel bars and spherical wooden beads, essential for constructing the manipulative tool. Additionally, technology resources such as instructional videos and digital platforms may be employed to enhance teaching and learning experiences. Human capital plays a crucial role, with educators serving as key stakeholders responsible for implementing the innovation in the classroom. Training and professional development programs may be offered to educators to build their capacity in effectively utilizing the innovation. Collaboration with educational experts and stakeholders further enriches the human capital aspect by providing valuable insights and support. Overall, the combination of material, technology, and human resources contributes to the successful creation and operation of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation, facilitating engaging and effective mathematics instruction.

Optimizing resource utilization involves implementing various strategies and techniques aimed at ensuring cost-effectiveness and sustainability in the long term. One approach is to conduct thorough needs assessments and feasibility studies to identify the most critical resources required for the innovation's development and implementation. By understanding the specific needs and requirements, resources can be allocated more efficiently, avoiding unnecessary expenditures. Additionally, embracing a culture of innovation and continuous improvement encourages stakeholders to explore creative solutions for resource optimization. This may involve reusing or repurposing existing materials and technology whenever possible, reducing the need for new acquisitions. Moreover, establishing partnerships and collaborations with external organizations or industry stakeholders can provide access to additional resources, expertise, and funding opportunities. Furthermore, implementing efficient project management practices, such as setting clear objectives, establishing timelines, and monitoring progress regularly, helps ensure that resources are used effectively throughout the project lifecycle. Continuous monitoring and evaluation allow for timely adjustments and reallocation of resources based on evolving needs and priorities.

Lastly, investing in capacity building and training initiatives for educators and other stakeholders fosters resource stewardship and sustainability. By equipping individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge, they can make informed decisions regarding resource utilization, ultimately contributing to the long-term success of the innovation.

e. Progress Monitoring

Monitoring the progress and outcomes of the innovation's implementation typically involves a collaborative effort

among various stakeholders, each with distinct roles and responsibilities. The project manager oversees the overall implementation, coordinating activities, setting timelines, allocating resources, and ensuring project objectives are met within specified deadlines. The implementation team, consisting of teachers, administrators, and staff members, executes specific strategies and activities outlined in the project plan, monitoring progress and reporting any issues to the project manager. A monitoring and evaluation officer designs frameworks, collects data, analyzes results, and provides regular reports to stakeholders on the innovation's effectiveness. Additionally, stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, students, parents, and community members, contribute input, feedback, and observations to assess impact and identify areas for improvement. External evaluators or consultants may also conduct independent evaluations, offering impartial insights and recommendations for enhancing effectiveness. Effective monitoring requires close collaboration, communication, and clear delineation of roles among stakeholders to ensure accountability and success.

To effectively monitor the progress and outcomes of the innovation's implementation, a comprehensive approach is adopted. This involves several key processes and methodologies: Data collection plays a pivotal role, employing both quantitative and qualitative methods such as surveys, assessments, interviews, focus groups, observations, and documentation review. These methods enable the gathering of relevant data on various aspects of the implementation process and its impact on student learning outcomes. Key performance indicators (KPIs) are defined to measure progress and success, aligned with the innovation's objectives. These metrics encompass student achievement scores, attendance rates, engagement levels, teacher satisfaction, and resource utilization, providing a holistic view of the innovation's performance. Regular monitoring is established to track activities and milestones throughout the implementation phase. This involves periodic check-ins, progress reports, and feedback sessions to ensure adherence to timelines, identify challenges, and address issues promptly. Formative assessments are conducted to assess student understanding and proficiency at different stages of implementation. These assessments inform adjustments to teaching strategies, curriculum delivery, and resource allocation based on student needs and feedback. Data analysis is crucial for deriving meaningful insights into the effectiveness of the innovation. Quantitative results are synthesized, and qualitative feedback is interpreted to identify trends, patterns, and areas for improvement, guiding decision-making and improvement efforts.

Stakeholder engagement is integral, involving teachers, students, parents, administrators, and community members in the evaluation process. Their input, perspectives, and experiences are solicited to gain a comprehensive understanding of the innovation's impact and areas for enhancement. Continuous improvement is emphasized, with evaluation findings informing iterative refinements to the innovation. Strengths and weaknesses are identified, corrective actions are implemented as needed, and strategies are refined to optimize outcomes and maximize impact over time. Through these processes and methodologies, education stakeholders can effectively monitor the progress and outcomes of the innovation's implementation, facilitating data-driven decision-

Innovation Output/Outcome

OUTPUTS/OUTCOMES (Enumerates the outputs or outcomes produce from this innovation)	Beneficiary/ies (who benefited from the corresponding results of outcome)
1. Development of manipulative materials: Creation of the JSA Fraction Beads, including the design, construction, and assembly of the manipulative materials.	1. Students: Students directly benefit from improved engagement, comprehension, and problem-solving skills in mathematics, leading to enhanced academic performance and numeracy skills.
2. Implementation in classrooms: Integration of the JSA Fraction Beads into mathematics instruction, including lesson planning and delivery	2. Teachers: Educators benefit from increased effectiveness in teaching mathematics, as well as professional development opportunities related to the implementation of innovative teaching strategies.
3. Enhanced student engagement: Increased student participation and interaction with mathematical concepts through hands-on manipulation of the fraction beads.	3. School Administrators: School leaders benefit from improved learning outcomes and student performance, contributing to the overall success and reputation of the educational institution.
4. Improved conceptual understanding: Deepened comprehension of abstract mathematical concepts, particularly fractions, decimals, and percentages, among students.	4. Parents and Guardians: Parents and guardians benefit from seeing their children develop a deeper understanding and appreciation of mathematics, leading to increased confidence and success in school.
5. Enhanced problem-solving skills: Development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities through application of mathematical concepts using the fraction beads.	5. Community: The wider community benefits from having a more numerate and skilled workforce, as well as the potential for increased educational opportunities and socioeconomic development.
6. Teacher professional development: Training and support provided to educators on effective utilization of the	

JSA Fraction Beads in teaching mathematics.	
7. Positive learning outcomes: Improved academic performance and numeracy skills demonstrated by students as a result of their engagement with the innovation.	
8. Sustainable implementation: Establishment of processes and procedures to ensure the continued use and effectiveness of the JSA Fraction Beads over time.	
9. Scalability and dissemination: Potential for replication and adoption of the innovation in other educational settings, leading to broader impact and reach.	

Fig. 20: Innovation Output/Outcome

making and continuous improvement in educational practice.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

To sustain the implementation of the JSA Fraction Beads innovation in the future, several key steps and actions are planned. Firstly, continuous training and professional development sessions will be conducted for teachers to ensure ongoing proficiency in utilizing the strategy effectively. This includes providing refresher courses, workshops, and access to additional resources or support materials as needed. Secondly, regular monitoring and evaluation processes will be established to assess the impact of the innovation on student learning outcomes and identify areas for improvement. Feedback mechanisms will also be implemented to gather insights from stakeholders and make necessary adjustments to enhance the strategy's effectiveness over time. Additionally, efforts will be made to secure funding or resources to maintain the availability and accessibility of the JSA Fraction Beads materials, ensuring sustainability in the long term. Collaboration with relevant stakeholders, including educational institutions, government agencies, and community organizations, will also be prioritized to garner support and promote widespread adoption of the innovation. By implementing these measures, the sustainability of the JSA Fraction Beads strategy can be ensured, leading to continued improvements in mathematics education and student success. These sus-

tainability actions are designed to address potential challenges or risks that may arise post-implementation by providing proactive measures to ensure the continued effectiveness and availability of the JSA Fraction Beads strategy. By offering ongoing training and professional development opportunities for teachers, the innovation remains relevant and adaptable to evolving educational needs and teaching practices. Regular monitoring and evaluation processes help identify any emerging issues or areas for improvement, allowing for timely adjustments to be made to optimize the strategy's impact. Feedback mechanisms facilitate communication with stakeholders, enabling the identification of potential challenges or concerns early on and the implementation of appropriate solutions. Securing funding or resources ensures the continued availability and accessibility of the JSA Fraction Beads materials, mitigating the risk of discontinuation due to financial constraints. Collaboration with relevant stakeholders fosters a supportive network that can collectively address challenges and sustain the momentum of the innovation. Overall, these sustainability actions proactively address potential challenges or risks post-implementation by promoting ongoing refinement, support, and collaboration to ensure the long-term success of the JSA Fraction Beads strategy.

Enhancement plans are integral to continuously improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the JSA Fraction Beads strategy over time. These plans involve ongoing research and development efforts aimed at refining the manipulative materials and instructional methods to better meet the evolving needs of educators and learners. Regular feedback mechanisms, such as surveys or focus groups, enable stakeholders to provide insights into their experiences with the strategy, informing targeted improvements and adjustments. Additionally, collaboration with educational experts and researchers allows for the integration of cutting-edge pedagogical techniques and best practices into the strategy's implementation. Continuous professional development opportunities for teachers ensure they are equipped with the latest knowledge and skills to effectively leverage the JSA Fraction Beads in their classrooms. Technology integration, such as digital tools or online resources, can further enhance the accessibility and versatility of the strategy, accommodating diverse learning preferences and environments. By systematically implementing these enhancement plans, the JSA Fraction Beads strategy can continually evolve to maximize its impact on mathematics education and address emerging challenges in teaching and learning. To further develop and refine the JSA Fraction Beads innovation for better outcomes, several strategies are proposed. Firstly, ongoing collaboration with educators, curriculum specialists, and researchers will facilitate the continuous improvement of instructional methods and materials. This collaborative approach ensures that the innovation remains aligned with educational standards and responsive to the changing needs of learners. Additionally, conducting regular evaluations and assessments allows for the identification of areas for improvement and refinement based on real-world implementation experiences. Integrating feedback from teachers and students enables targeted adjustments to be made to the strategy, enhancing its effectiveness and usability in diverse educational contexts. Furthermore, investing in professional development opportunities for educators ensures they are

equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to implement the innovation effectively. By systematically implementing these strategies, the JSA Fraction Beads innovation can undergo continuous development and refinement, ultimately leading to better outcomes for learners in mathematics education.

As the JSA Fraction Beads innovation continues to be implemented and refined, several desirable outcomes are envisioned to evolve over time. Initially, we anticipate an immediate improvement in students' conceptual understanding of mathematical concepts, particularly fractions, decimals, and percentages. As educators become more adept at integrating the JSA Fraction Beads into their teaching practices, we expect to see a sustained increase in student engagement and motivation in mathematics lessons.

Over the long term, we envision a positive impact on students' mathematical proficiency, reflected in improved academic performance and standardized test scores. Moreover, as the innovation becomes more widely adopted across educational settings, we anticipate a cultural shift towards more experiential and hands-on approaches to mathematics instruction. Ultimately, we envision the JSA Fraction Beads innovation contributing to a more holistic and effective approach to mathematics education, empowering students with the skills and confidence needed to succeed in their academic pursuits and beyond.